

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL: DETECTABILITY OF VARIED HYBRIDIZATION SCENARIOS USING GENOME-SCALE HYBRID DETECTION METHODS

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Reproducing the power calculations in [2]

Our original simulations involved only the networks n10h2, n15h3 and n25h5. We noticed HyDe's low precision and high false negative rates which contradicted the positive results found in [2]. We then decided to reproduce the power calculations in [2] as shown in Figure 1 and decided to include the networks n4h1, n4h1_{introgression}, n5h2 and n8h3 in the simulation study. We discovered that HyDe has good performance when the parent-hybrid relationship is clearly specified, and it is unable to detect hybrid relationships involving ghost lineages. We note that these simulations were done with hybrid-lambda, rather than ms.

References

- [1] Silas Bossert, Elizabeth A. Murray, Alain Pauly, Kyrilo Chernyshov, Seán G. Brady, and Bryan N. Danforth. Gene tree estimation error with ultraconserved elements: An empirical study on pseudapis bees. *Systematic Biology*, 70(4):803–821, 12 2020.
- [2] Sungsik Kong and Laura S. Kubatko. Comparative performance of popular methods for hybrid detection using genomic data. *Systematic Biology*, 70(5):891–907, 01 2021.
- [3] Claudia Solís-Lemus and Cécile Ané. Inferring phylogenetic networks with maximum pseudolikelihood under incomplete lineage sorting. *PLOS Genetics*, 12(3):e1005896–, 03 2016.

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Figure 1: Power of HyDe test on detecting a single hybridization event by mixing parameter. This test is performed on a gene trees generated from a species topology $(O : 2.0, ((P1 : 0.50, \#H1 : 0 :: \gamma) : 0.50, (P2 : 0.5, (HYB : 0.5)\#H1 : 0 :: 1 - \gamma) : 0.5) : 1.0)$. This topology has relatively shorter branch lengths than those tested in other networks in this paper. It has four taxa and one hybridization event.

Method	Complexity	Assumptions	Input	Test	Output
TICR	$O(gn^4)$	Equidistant network: No; Number of gene flow events: Any	Population tree and gene trees	If observed qcCFs align with expected CFs under IL-S-only MSC	p-values from individual quartet tests and overall p-value reporting goodness-of-fit to population tree
MSCquartets	$O(gn^4)$	Equidistant network: No; Number of gene flow events: Any	Gene trees	If observed qcCFs align with expected CFs under IL-S-only MSC	p-values from individual quartet tests
HyDe	$O(Ln^3)$	Equidistant network: Yes; Number of gene flow events: One	Sequences from taxa and outgroup	Hills statistic evaluates triples for site pattern frequencies against phylogenetic invariants	List of all triples with 1) proposed hybrid speciation (parental and hybrid lineages), 2) a estimated γ , and 3) p-value
Patterson's D	$O(Ln^3)$	Equidistant network: Yes; Number of gene flow events: One	Sequences from taxa and outgroup	Excess in site pattern frequencies of <i>ABBA</i> and <i>BABA</i> when expected to be equal	A D -statistic per triple, which when mapped to a z-distribution provides a p-value
D_3	$O(Ln^3)$	Equidistant network: Yes; Number of gene flow events: One	Sequences	If triples reject IL-S-only assumption (measured as deviation of D_3 from 0)	Distribution of D_3 values of triples, which when mapped to a z-distribution provides a p-value
D_p	$O(Ln^3)$	Equidistant network: Yes; Number of gene flow events: One	Sequences from taxa and outgroup	Excess in site pattern frequencies of <i>ABBA</i> and <i>BABA</i> when expected to be equal	A D_p value per triple, which when mapped to a z-distribution provides a p-value

Table 1: Summary Table of Hybrid Detection Methods

Figure 2: Precision, recall, false positive rate for MSCquartets (from true and estimated gene trees), HyDe, 's D-Statistic, and D_3 on the networks: $n4h1_{\text{introgression}}$ (network with single shallow hybridization event), $n5h2$ (network with two overlapping hybridization events), $n8h3$ (network with three overlapping hybridization events), and $n25h5$ (network with five overlapping hybridization events). All tests are Bonferroni-corrected at a level of significance $\alpha = 0.05/\text{number of tests}$ (see Figure 8 in the Supplementary materials for results on $\alpha = 0.05$). For HyDe, an additional metric, Wrong Hybrid Rate (blue) describes the rate at which hybridization is detected but is falsely attributed to the incorrect hybrid taxon. For the introgression event ($n4h1_{\text{introgression}}$), MSCquartets, HyDe, Patterson's D-Statistic, and D_3 all behave similarly to the hybrid speciation scenario in $n4h1$, with near-perfect recovery and identification of hybrid scenarios. High recall is noted for $n5h2$ across MSCquartets and D-related methods. For $n5h2$, HyDe correctly recovers parent-hybrid relationships, but has a slightly lower recall. Network $n8h3$ displays elevated false negative rates across all methods. However, precision is high, and recall between all methods are comparable.

Figure 4: (a) Network n10h2 replicated from [3] with ten taxa and two hybridization events, its singular hybridizations, (b) n10h1_{shallow} and (c) n10h1_{deep}, and the largest network tested, (d) n25h5. All branches are labeled in coalescent units. Network n10h1_{shallow} (b) is the n10h2 network containing only the shallowest hybridization ($\gamma = 0.2$), which impacts one taxon, labeled 9. Network n10h1_{deep} (c) is a derivation the n10h2 network containing only the deepest hybridization event ($\gamma = 0.3$), which impacts taxa 3-9. Network n25h5 (d) contains 25 taxa and five hybridization events, three of which impact only a singular downstream taxon (from top to bottom, $\gamma = 0.369, 0.449, 0.395$), with two that are deeper in the tree (from top to bottom, $\gamma = 0.024, 0.334$), creating overlapping hybridization events.

Figure 5: (a) Network n15h3 replicated from [3] with 15 taxa and 3 hybridizations events, and its singular hybridizations, (b) n15h1_{shallow}, (c) n15h1_{intermediate}, and (d) n15h1_{deep}. All branches are labeled in coalescent units. Network n15h1_{shallow} (b) is the n15h3 network containing only the shallowest hybridization ($\gamma = 0.2$), which impacts only taxon 10. Network n15h1_{intermediate} (c) is the n15h3 network with only the intermediate-depth hybridization ($\gamma = 0.2$) impacting the clade (2,3). Network n15h1_{deep} (d) is the n15h3 network with only the deepest hybridization event ($\gamma = 0.3$), impacting the clade (2,3,4,5,6).

Figure 6: Precision, recall, false positive rate for MSCQuartets (from true and estimated gene trees), HyDe, Patterson’s D-Statistic, D_p , and D_3 on the n4h1 network with mixing parameters $\gamma \in 0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5$, where 0 depicts no gene flow, and 0.5 depicts equal contribution from both parental lineages. All tests are Bonferroni-corrected at a level of significance $\alpha = 0.05/\text{number of tests}$ (see Figure 7 in the Supplementary materials for results on $\alpha = 0.05$). For HyDe, an additional metric, Wrong Hybrid Rate describes the rate at which hybridization is detected but is falsely attributed to the incorrect hybrid taxon. In the absence of gene flow, HyDe and D_3 have the lowest proportion of false positives, but the difference is not considerable when compared to that of Patterson’s D-statistic and MSCQuartets. With all other levels of admixture, as both admixture and sample size increases, all tests display an increased recall and decreased false positive rates. In cases where gene flow is present, D_3 requires slightly higher sequence lengths to eliminate false negatives when compared to Patterson’s D-Statistic. However, given a sufficient sequence length, all tests are able to reliably detect the presence of hybridization.

Figure 7: Precision, recall, false positive rate for MSCQuartets (from true and estimated gene trees), HyDe, 's D-Statistic, and D₃ on the n4h1 network with mixing parameters $\gamma \in 0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5$, where 0 depicts no gene flow, and 0.5 depicts equal contribution from both parental lineages. For HyDe, an additional metric, Wrong Hybrid Rate describes the rate at which hybridization is detected but is falsely attributed to the incorrect hybrid taxon. All tests are at a level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$. Non-zero false positive rates can be seen in the case of zero gene flow for all but D₃. As gene flow and amount of genetic information increases, each method displays a decrease in false negative rate.

Figure 8: Precision, recall, false positive rate for MSCQuartets (from true and estimated gene trees), HyDe, 's D-Statistic, and D_3 on the networks: $n4h1_{\text{introg}}$ (network with single shallow hybridization event), $n5h2$ (network with two overlapping hybridization events), $n8h3$ (network with three overlapping hybridization events), and $n25h5$ (network with five overlapping hybridization events). All tests are at a level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$. Each method performs well on the introgression event of $n4h1$, and $n5h2$ with some false negatives seen with HyDe. Each method has a similar recall for $n8h3$, with precision near 100% for all but HyDe, which still had 75% precision at minimum for all sequence lengths.

Figure 9: Precision, recall, false positive rate for MSCQuartets (from true and estimated gene trees), HyDe, 's D-Statistic, and D_3 on the networks: n_{10h2} , $n_{10h1_{shallow}}$ (n_{10h2} with only the shallow hybridization event), $n_{10h1_{deep}}$ (n_{10h2} with only the deeper hybridization event). All tests are at a level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$. D_3 performs well on n_{10h2} and its singular hybridizations $n_{10h1_{shallow}}$ and $n_{10h1_{deep}}$ relative to other methods given its high precision. In contrast, Patterson's D-Statistic has slightly higher false positives, at the cost of precision. MSCQuartets also has increased false positive and low recall. HyDe has lower recall for n_{10h2} and $n_{10h1_{shallow}}$. There are also high false positives (20%) in the case of n_{10h2} , with a pattern for hybrid clade misidentification more frequently than precise identification of hybrid clades.

Figure 10: Precision, recall, false positive rate for MSCquartets (from true and estimated gene trees), HyDe, 's D-Statistic, and D_3 on the networks: $n15h_3$, $n15h_{1\text{deep}}$ ($n15h_3$ with only the deepest hybridization event), $n15h_{1\text{shallow}}$ ($n15h_3$ with only the shallowest hybridization event), and $n15h_{1\text{intermediate}}$ ($n15h_3$ with a hybridization event of intermediate depth). All tests are at a level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$. D_3 has the highest and most stable precision across all $n15h_3$ and single hybrid derivatives. Recall remains similar across all tests, with the exception of Patterson's D-Statistic on $n15h_3$, which is slightly higher, paired with a higher false positive rate. Patterson's D-Statistic also shows decreased precision scores. MSCquartets' precision remains high (80%) in all cases except $n15h_{1\text{intermediate}}$. HyDe also has a lower precision, around 10% – 25% across all network formats.

Figure 11: Left: Phylogenetic tree of selected species from the bee subfamily Nomiinae, as provided by [1]. Letters A-C identify nodes that were identified as conflicting relationships by the analyses conducted in [1]. Right: Heatmap of frequency of taxa identified as part of hybridization events (scaled between 0 and 1 for comparison across methods). MSCquartets was conducted with gene trees estimated using the IQTree2-GTRG model. Tests are performed at significance level $\alpha = 0.05$.